

**ANALYSIS OF FOREIGN LITERATURE ON SPEECH DEVELOPMENT
OF CHILDREN WITH HEARING DEFECTS**

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Introduction

Philology (Greek: philologia - love of words, affection for words) is a general science consisting of the cooperation of humanities - linguistics, literary studies, textual studies, source studies, paleography and others; studies the history and essence of human spiritual culture by linguistic and stylistic analysis of written monuments. The text, which consists of the sum of its internal issues and external relations, is the first basis that determines the existence of philology.

The process of language acquisition in society takes place in the conditions of mutual speech activity (communication) of people. Human hearing is very important in this process. After all, it is one of the main factors in the formation and development of spoken speech. Accordingly, this issue has been the focus of attention of scientists and pedagogues who have lived in different periods of the development of society. The problems of theory and practice of teaching and educating the deaf have a long history and are characterized by different approaches.

If we pay attention to the philological point of view, the means of communication with hearing impaired people created an environment similar to the process of learning a new language. In ancient Greece and Rome, there was no system of education for children with hearing problems. In ancient countries, deaf-mutes were not recognized as full members of society and they were considered "uneducable". In the Justinian Code of the 6th century BC, it was mentioned that guardianship should be established over "minors", congenital deaf as those who cannot act independently. That is, such persons were considered to be unable to manage their property because they were "those who could not speak, and could

not express their thoughts in writing or verbally." In the "medical" science of ancient times, there was an opinion that deafness has an unusual nature and cannot be corrected. From historical sources, we can see that a special attitude towards the deaf arose from the 9th-8th centuries BC. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle (384-322 BC) in his works such as "Feelings of the Feelers" and "Emotional Perception and its Objects" thought about the reasons for the mutual dependence of the sense organs and considered deafness and dumbness as a child's mental condition. revealed the negative impact on their abilities. The philosopher's "discovery" that the non-existence of one of the organs of human perception or its violation destroys integrity and wholeness unknowingly became the basis for the emergence of the first deaf-pedagogical doctrine. The scientist emphasizes that the derailment of the activity of one of the sense organs does not allow the general development of a person and evaluates the auditory analyzer as follows: "Sound is a means of thinking, and hearing is an important organ for understanding the world around us. In connection with this, it can be said that a person who has not heard since birth is naturally dumb." Aristotle, while revealing the nature of the negative impact of deafness and dumbness on the child's mental activity, notes that dumbness is a consequence of congenital deafness.

With the emergence of Christianity, a compassionate attitude toward people with developmental problems began to form, but at the same time, various negative religious beliefs about such persons and their disabilities began to appear. For example, according to these views, children with deafness were seen as "God's punishment" sent by God in return for the sins of their parents. At the beginning of the Middle Ages in Europe, the traditions of limiting the rights of persons with various developmental problems began to form. Medieval religious philosophers began to prove the theory that people with congenital defects are not full human beings, and the jurisprudence of this period considered disabled people as those who cannot answer for their actions, and the law made such people self-governing. did not recognize as individuals. The first attempts to educate the hearing impaired date back to the 15th century. The theory and practice of teaching and educating the deaf, which arose in Western Europe, attracted many scientists of that time.

The Dutch scientist Rudolph Agricola (1443-1485) in his book "On the Discovery of Dialectic" thinks about teaching the deaf to written speech using special methods and methods and gives specific examples in this regard. The Italian professor Girolamo Cardano, who had an important place in the theory and practice of teaching and educating the deaf, was the owner of another brilliant activity

experience. The scientist explained the physiological causes of deaf-mute in his works such as "On Refinements", "On the Physiology of Sensations", and "About My Life" and revealed the fact that deafness is caused by illness, and muteness is a consequence of deafness. The initial classification of deafness was created as a result of the birth of the children of Girolamo Cardano as deaf-mute and the father's attempts to "bring them back to life". According to this classification, the deaf are divided into the following categories:

- a) born deaf;
- b) early hearing loss (before the child learns to speak) and late hearing loss;
- c) late-onset hearing loss with preserved speech.

The scientist was also the first in history to show the physiological basis of deafness and dumbness and proved the possibilities of teaching the deaf based on healthy sense organs. For the first time, he puts forward the idea of a differentiated approach to teaching, taking into account the level of hearing ability and the levels of speech development. J. Cardano's theoretical views found practical proof in Spain. Pedro Ponso De Leon (1520-1584) creates an original method of teaching the deaf and successfully implements the experience of teaching children of wealthy families individually. P. Ponso uses different forms of speech in his methodology: oral, written, dactyl and gesture.

H. P. Bonet (1579-1633) in his work "The nature of sounds and the art of teaching the deaf and dumb to speak" written in 1620, considered the goals and tasks of teaching and educating the deaf at that time. talks about the need to teach conversational speech through dactyl and its oral form. He considers the activities aimed at the development of speech, conducted by a special teacher using the form of questions and answers, as a factor of special attention to the impact of children's mental development. E.R. Carrion (1579-1652) used the rich experience of his contemporaries to develop their ideas, relying on tactile-vibration sensations and auditory remnants in the education of the deaf. John Wallis (1616-1703) and D. Bulwer from England, D. K. Ammann (1669-1724) from Switzerland, F. M. Van Helmont (1614-1699) from the Netherlands, F. L. Tersi from Italy (1631-1687) contributed to the further development of H. P. Bonnet's ideas.) have made contributions as separate attempts to educate the deaf.

Attempts to educate the deaf individually were the objective reason for the social order of nobles who had hearing impaired children. Therefore, although individual

education has a positive experience, it was not possible to establish educational institutions for children of this category for a long time. Only in the 70s of the 18th century, attempts to establish and develop special institutions for the education and upbringing of deaf children began to appear. In 1770, Charles Michel de Epe (1712-1789), the first private school in the world history, opened in Paris - the Deaf and Dumb Institute. De Epe created a method of mimicry guided by the ideas of French intellectuals such as Voltaire, Denis Diderot, and Jean Jacques Rousseau. Charles Michel de Epe's ideas were developed by his student RA Sicard. In the teaching system, the practicing scientist focuses on the mental and physical development of deaf children in all aspects. This system prepares the deaf child to acquire knowledge of general education subjects, to live and work in society. But in order to solve these tasks, only the sign form of speech is used during teaching, and deaf students learn to write based on it. RA Sikar enriches the sign language with "methodical signs". That is, in the process of teaching based on this method, students are taught certain symbols to describe grammatical categories in the language. It is known that there are many grammatical categories in the language. As a result of not being able to master the signs, the number of students is increasing day by day, they do not have time to master the knowledge of subjects, and despite the improvement of the teaching system based on the sign method, its practical use does not fulfill the tasks set before education. shows that it does not allow to solve the problem. On April 14, 1778, Samuel Heinike (1727-1790) founded the Deaf and Dumb Institute in Leipzig, Germany. Samuil Geinike creates his own teaching system of teaching the deaf, which was later called the "pure oral method", which occupies an important place in the history of deaf pedagogy. This method recognizes the spoken word as the main means and goal of teaching the deaf. Children also learn reading, writing and arithmetic in this system. This method of teaching the deaf is based on the technique of mechanical exercises for pronouncing sounds, syllables, words and sentences. That is, intensive work is carried out on pronunciation skills of deaf children in the initial period of education. Acquiring knowledge of general education subjects depends on learning pronunciation skills.

Johann Fatter (1842-1916), on the other hand, takes teaching to master oral speech as the main goal of teaching. He bases the teaching of the deaf on oral speech and speech sounds. Later, I. Fatter's system received the second name "Sound Method". The first institution (school) for the deaf in the United States was opened in 1817 by Thomas Gallode (1787-1851). In this educational institution, education is conducted based on the French method using writing, gestures and typing. Later,

Horace Man (1796-1859) and Edward Gallodeler (1837-1907), who had the opportunity to study and analyze the experiences of a number of schools personally and on a business trip to Western European countries, based on the combination of different methods, "Combined (unified) method" they create This system includes various methods, including oral training. Alexander Melville Bell (1815-1905) also dealt with ways to solve the problems of teaching deaf children to speak, and he proposed the "Visible Speech" system. In it, each sound articulation has its own reflected sign. Alexander Graham Bell (1847-1922), successor to his father A.M. Bell, founded the Physio-Phonetic Institute and the Society for Aiding the Teaching of Speech to the Deaf, invented the telephone, and helped the deaf he also paid great attention to the issues of teaching from a young age. In 1879, Paris, the capital of France, and in 1880, in Milan, Italy, the first congresses devoted to the education of the deaf were held. According to the decision of the Milan conference, the "Pure oral method" system is recognized as universal (convenient, most effective) due to the fact that it allows deaf people to communicate with hearing people. The achievements at the end of this period were such that a positive attitude towards the education of the deaf was formed in each country, and laws on "free, compulsory universal primary education" were adopted. That is, this period is characterized by the establishment of state institutions for the deaf and dumb, the adoption of laws, the determination of the sources of material support for education, the development of the goals and methods of education. Special education has begun to cover more and more large areas of the European and American continents, and the formation of non-governmental organizations will give impetus to the future development of the system of education and upbringing of the deaf. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, European and American deaf pedagogues tried to eliminate the existing superficiality in the "Pure Oral Method" system and to improve it. Because this system had the main goal of teaching deaf people to speak, it did not allow children to learn general education subjects. The German teacher of the deaf, I. Heidzik (1851-1942), criticizes the "pure oral method" as a method that does not correspond to the nature of a deaf child with a hearing impairment.

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